

Application of Wet Fixation and Drying Treatment of Cotton Fabric with Reactive Dye and Find Out the Suitable Condition Based on L9 Control- Level Factor Design

Dipta Barua^{1*}, Md. Iusuf Khan², Sattyajit Sikder³, Avijit Dev³, Rabaca Sultana³
Taryqul Islam Aulve³, Mehedi Hasan Ibhanraj³, Tonmoy Palit³

¹Bachelor of Textile Engineering- Port City International University

²Masters of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering- Wuhan Textile University China

³Bachelor of Textile Engineering -Port City International University.

Abstract: The conventional dyeing process requires a substantial amount of auxiliaries and water, which leaches hazardous colored effluents to the environment. Herein, a newly developed sustainable spray dyeing system has been proposed for cotton fabric in the presence of reactive dyes, which has the potential to minimize the textile dyeing industries environmental impact in terms of water consumption and save significant energy. The results suggest that fresh dye solution can be mixed with an alkali solution before spray dyeing to avoid the reactive dye hydrolysis phenomenon. After that, color spray on the cotton knitted fabric by cold pad batch method. To find out the K/S value based on single factor analysis and L9 design analysis.

Keywords: Cotton knit fabrics, Reactive blue, Spray dyeing, K/S value, Single Factors, L9 design analysis

*Corresponding Author: Dipto Barua: b.diptaaa@gmail.com

Accepted: 19 May, 2023; **Published:** 31 May, 2023

How to cite this article: Dipta Barua, Md. Iusuf Khan, Sattyajit Sikder, Avijit Dev, Rabaca Sultana, Taryqul Islam Aulve, Mehedi Hasan Ibhanraj, Tonmoy Palit (2023). Application of Wet Fixation and Drying Treatment of cotton fabric with Reactive Dye and Find Out the Suitable Condition Based on L9 Control- Level Factors Design. *North American Academic Research*, 6(5), 99-124. [doi: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7995061](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7995061)

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

1. Cotton knit fabrics:

Single Jersey cotton Knitted fabric is a textile that results from knitting, the process of inter-looping of yarns or inter-meshing of loops[1]. Its properties are distinct from woven fabric in that it is more flexible and can be more readily constructed into smaller pieces, making it ideal for socks and hats. Cotton knits are a soft knit which commonly comes in jersey, rib and interlock weaves. A cotton knit can also have spandex making it move with you. 100% cotton knits are suitable for loungewear, tops and children's wear. Cotton/spandex knits are great for tops, dresses, skirts, leggings, loungewear and children's wear[2]. We also like using some cotton knits for collars, cuffs and waistbands. Knit fabric is an elastic material, made by yarns initially formed into loops and then interconnected in order to produce a textile structure[3]. Knit fabrics do not have a weave. However, the system of weft and warp threads, traditional for other fabric types, is preserved. The feature of knitwear is that it can stretch as you like due to the loops, which can change the size and shape. The main raw materials for knit fabrics are silk, linen, cotton, wool, viscose, rayon and more[4]. Manufacturers add various synthetic materials to achieve the best combination of quality and durability.

Let's talk about types and uses of knit fabrics, pros and cons, trends and life hacks which help you make a dress or sweater you long dreamed of. There are two main ways of manufacturing of knit fabrics: warp knitting (vertical set of yarns) and weft knitting (horizontal set of yarns)[5]. The ways differ with the process of knitting. In warp knitting, each thread has its needle and the fabric is knitted in the lengthwise direction (vertically). Weft knitted fabrics are made of one thread interlocked horizontally. Here are the most popular types of knitted fabrics. A dye, which is capable of reacting chemically with a substrate to form a covalent dye substrate linkage, is known as reactive dyes[6]. The reactive dyes constitute the most commonly used class of dyes for dyeing cellulosic textiles, because of their good all-round properties, such as water solubility, ease of application, variety of application methods, availability of different shades, brightness of color shades, good to excellent wash and light fastness and moderate price. Reactive dyes may have poor fastness to chlorine bleach. Here the dye contains a reactive group and this reactive group makes covalent bond with the fibre polymer and act as an integral part of fibre[7]. This covalent bond is formed between the dye molecules and the terminal -OH (hydroxyl) group of cellulosic fibres or between the dye molecules and the terminal -NH₂ (amino) group of polyamide or wool fibres.

1.1 Reaction:

Here,

D= dye part.

Wool = wool polymer.

Cell = cellulosic polymer.

Reactive dyes are so called because this is the only type of dye, which has reactive group, and that reactive group reacts chemically with fibre polymer molecules and form covalent bond[8]. This covalent bond is formed between the reactive group and terminal -OH (Hydroxyl) group of cellulosic fibre and wool fiber or between reactive group and terminal -NH₂ (Amino) group of polyamide polymer. The strength of this covalent bond is more than ionic bond, hydrogen bond and Vander Waal's force of attraction. Thus the reactive group becomes an integral part of the fibre.

For this reasons the dyes are so called. They are also called 'fibre reactive group'. On the occasion of 100 year's celebration of synthetic dyes manufacturing, two chemists of ICI Company (UK) named Stephen and Rattee tried to manufacture a new dyestuff. Thus they succeed to invent a new dye in 1965, which was named REACTIVE DYE. This was manufacture for dyeing cellulosic fabrics. The first three reactive dyes were PROCION YELLOWR, PROCION BRILLIANT RED 2B and PROCION BLUE 3G for this effort they were awarded gold medal of the society of dyes and colorists for the year 1960[9].

Reactive are mostly used for dyeing cellulosic fibers. At past cellulosic fibers were dyed with direct and vat dyes, but after the introduction of reactive dyes there utility has become limited. Reactive dyes are superior to direct dye in the following aspects: Ability to procedure bright shades of wide range.

1. Good washing fastness.
2. Good light fastness.

And it is superior to vat dyes in the following aspects:

1. Simple dyeing method therefore one stage dyeing.
2. Low temperature dyeing (below 1000C)
3. Lower cost, i.e. cheaper.

1.2 Properties or Characteristics of reactive dye:

1. Reactive dyes are cationic dyes, which are used for dyeing cellulose, protein and polyamide fibres.
2. Reactive dyes are found in power, liquid and print paste form.
3. During dyeing the reactive group of this dye forms covalent bond with fibre polymer and becomes an integral parts of the fibre.
4. Reactive dyes are soluble in water.
5. They have very good light fastness with rating about 6. The dyes have very stable electron arrangement and can protect the degrading effect of ultra-violet ray.
6. Textile materials dyed with reactive dyes have very good wash fastness with rating about 4-5 due to strong covalent bonds formed between fibre polymer and reactive group of dye.
7. Reactive dye gives brighter shades and has moderate rubbing fastness.
8. Dyeing method of reactive dyes is easy. It requires less time and low temperature for dyeing.
9. Reactive dyes are comparatively cheap
10. Reactive dyes have good perspiration fastness with rating 4-5.
11. Reactive dyes have good perspiration fastness.

1.3 General structure of reactive dyes:

The general structure of reactive dye is: D-B-G-X.

Fig. 1: Chemical structure of reactive dye

Here,

- D = Dye part or chromogen (color producing part).
Dyes may be direct, acid, disperse, premetallised dye etc.
- B = Bridging part.
Bridging part may be $-NH-$ group or $-NR-$ group.
- G = Reactive group bearing part.
- X= reactive group.

1.4 Classification of reactive dyes:

Reactive dyes may be classified in various ways as below:

A. On the basis of reactive group:

a. Halogen (commonly chlorine) derivatives of nitrogen containing heterocycle, like 3 types-

1. Triazine group
2. Pyridimine group
3. Quinoxaline dyes

Example:

- Triazine derivatives: procion, cibacron.
- Pyridimine derivatives: reactone
- Quinoxaline derivatives: levafix.

b. Activated vinyl compound:

1. Vinyl sulphone
2. Vinyl acrylamide
3. Vinyl sulphonamide.

Example:

- Vinyl sulphone: remazol
- Vinyl acrylamide: primazine
- Vinyl sulphonamide: levafix.

B. On the basis of reactivity:

1. Lower reactive dye: Here pH is maintained 12-12.5 by using NaOH in bath.
2. Medium reactive dye: here pH is maintained 11-12 by using Na₂CO₃ in dye bath.
3. Higher reactive dye: here pH is maintained 10-11 by using NaHCO₃ in dye bath.

C. On the basis of dyeing temperature:

a. Cold brand:

These types of dyes contain reactive group of high reactivity. So dyeing can be done in lower temperature i.e. 320-600C.

For example: PROCION M, LIVAFIX E.

Medium brand:

This type of dyes contains reactive groups of moderate reactivity. So dyeing is done in higher temperature than that of cold brand dyes i.e. in between 600-710C temperatures.

For example, Remazol, Livafix are medium brand dyes

b. Hot brand:

This type of dye contains reactive groups of least reactivity. So high temperature is required for dyeing i.e. 720-930C temperature is required for dyeing.

For example PRICION H, CIBACRON are hot brand dyes.

Characteristics of reactive group of reactive dye:

1. The characteristics of reactive group of dye are mentioned below:
2. Reactive groups do not contribute to the color of dye. Chromogen group imparts it.
3. The reactivity of vinyl sulphone group is less than that of halogen group.
4. If no of reactive group increases, binding also increases depending on dye structure.
5. Reactive dye absorb up to 90%.
6. Molecular weight of reactive group 69-211gm/ mole.
7. Bond energy of halogen groups are as below:
 - F (Fluorine)- 102-kcal/ gm
 - Cl (chlorine) – 74-kcal/ gm
 - Br (bromine) – 64-kcal/ gm
 - I (iodine) – 56-kcal/ gm
8. If the molecular weight of reactive group increases, reactivity also increases.
9. Reactivity of iodine is high but rate of hydrolysis is also high.
10. Chlorine imparts medium reactivity, but it is cheap and hydrolysis rate is medium.
11. Reactivity of fluorine is the least and its rate hydrolysis is also less.
12. Reactivity of vinyl sulphone group increases with increasing temperature and pH.
13. Sulphone group has more solubility but it is not stable.
14. Generally low molecular weight dyes are of hot brand.
15. Less affinity dyes are used for pad method.

1.5 Assistants used for dyeing with reactive dyes:

The following assistants are used in dye bath for dyeing with reactive dyes.

Salt:

The salts do the following things-

- Salts are used to increase the affinity of dye to fibre.
- It decreases the hydrolysis rate of dyes.
- It neutralizes the electro negativity of fibre surface when immersed in solution.
- It puts extra energy to push the dye inside the fibre polymer i.e. increase absorption of dye.

The amount of salt and used depends upon the shade to be produced.

- For light shade – 10gm/ L salt is used.
- For medium shade – 20 gm/ L salt is used.
- For dark shade – 30gm/L salt is used.

Alkali:

Alkali is used for the following purposes:

- Alkali is used to maintain proper pH in dye bath and thus to create alkaline condition.
- Alkali is used as a dye-fixing agent.
- Without alkali no dyeing take place.
- The strength of alkali used depends on the reactivity of dyes.

- As strong alkali caustic soda is used to create pH 12.5-12.
- As medium alkali soda ash (Na_2CO_3) is used to create pH 11-12 when dye is of medium reactivity.

As weak alkali NaHCO_3 is used to create pH 10-11 when dye is highly reactive

Urea:

Urea is used in continuous method of dyeing. It helps to get required shade of dye. To get dark shade more urea is used and to get light shade less amount of urea is used.

Soaping:

By soaping, the extra color is removed from fibre surface. Thus washing fastness is improved. Soaping increases the brightness and stability of the dye.

1.6 Factors considered for selection of dyes:

Dye selection depends upon the following factors:

Selection of dyeing method:

Dye selection depends on dyeing method, which may be:

- Batch wise/ discontinuous method
- Semi-continuous method i.e.
 - Pad – batch method
 - Pad – jig method
 - Pad – roll method
- Continuous method i.e.
 - Pad – steam method
 - Pad – dry method
 - Pad – thermo fix method

This dyeing method selection depends on:

1. Speed of dye diffusion on the fibre.
2. Affinity of dye to fibre
3. Reactivity to dye stuff.

Selection of brand:

Brand selection is important. It may be

- d. Hot brand – Less reactive dye (temp 72-93)
- e. Medium brand – Medium reactive dye.
- f. Cold brand – Most reactive dye.

3. Economy of production

4. Availability of dyes

5. Storage of dyes.

6. Bond stability i.e. kind of bonding

7. Fastness of dye i.e. washes, light, rubbing fastness

8. Re – producibility.

Reaction manner of dye and cellulose: The bonding behavior of dye and cellulose are mentioned below:

1. Hydroxyl group of cotton polymer takes part in reaction with reactive group of dye

2. Reactive group of dye react preferably with the hydroxyl group of cellulose than that of water.
3. The activation energy of dye – water reaction is 16.4 – 26.2 kcal and that of dye cellulose is 9.2 – 15.8 kcal. As the latter is less, so that occurs predominately.
4. Higher activation energy causes slower reaction.
5. The reaction with water and dye takes place in a smaller extent.
6. The strength of covalent bond formed between cellulose polymer and reactive group is more than hydrogen bonding, vander wall’s force of attraction and metal co-ordination bonds.
7. Extreme acidic and alkaline condition should be avoided, otherwise hydrolysis will take place resulting bond breakage and poor wash fastness.

1.7 Criteria for cellulose for attracting reactive dye:

The chemical structure of cellulose macromolecule is given below:

In cellulose macromolecule glucose units are linked through oxygen bridges formed between C1 position of one glucose and C4 position of adjacent glucose unit. Each glucose unit contains one primary hydroxyl group (at C6 position) and two secondary hydroxyl group =CHOH (at C2 and C3 positions)[10]. Again one end of this glucose unit has an additional secondary hydroxyl group at C4 position and the other end has an aldehyde or hemiacetal group at C1 position.

1.8 Now the following things are considered:

- Primary hydroxyl group (-CH₂OH) at C6 position is more reactive then the secondary hydroxyl groups (-CHOH) at C2 and C3 positions.
- C2 hydroxyl group is supported to be more acidic than C3 hydroxyl group under suitable alkaline condition and hence is more reactive.
- The hemiacetal group at C1 position is the most active while the additional hydroxyl group of C4 position is the least reactive.
- The reaction between reactive group and cellulose takes place predominantly with primary hydroxyl group to some extent.
- Longer carbon chain lowers the rate of reaction.
- Incase of monochloro triazinyl dyes, this reaction takes place 15 times more frequently with C6 hydroxyl group than with the hydroxyl group at C2 or C3 position.
- In case of dichlorotriazinyl dyes, this reaction takes place 3-7 times more frequently with hydroxyl group at C2 position than that with hydroxyl group at C1 or C3 position.

1.9 The reactive rate of some compounds are mentioned below:

COMPOUND	STRUCTURE	REACTIVE RATE
Water	H-OH	1.0
Iso-propanol	CH ₃ -CHOH-CH ₃	0.7
Ethanol	CH ₃ -CH ₂ -OH	7.4
Methanol	H-CH ₂ -OH	12.3
Glucose	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆	5.5

So from the above table it is obvious that secondary hydroxyl group is the most reactive while primary one is the least reactive.

1.10 Dyeing mechanism of reactive dye:

The dyeing mechanism of material with reactive dye takes place in 3 stages:-

1. Exhaustion of dye in presence of electrolyte or dye absorption.
2. Fixation under the influence of alkali.
3. wash-off the unfixed dye from material surface.

1. Dye absorption:

When fibre is immersed in dye liquor, an electrolyte is added to assist the exhaustion of dye. Here NaCl is used as the electrolyte. This electrolyte neutralize the negative charge formed in the fibre surface and puts extra energy to increase dye absorption. So when the textile material is introduced to dye liquor the dye is exhausted on to the fibre.

2. Fixation:

Fixation of dye means the reaction of reactive group of dye with terminal -OH or -NH₂ group of fibre and thus forming strong covalent bond with the fibre. This is an important phase, which is controlled by maintaining proper pH by adding alkali. The alkali used for this purpose depends on brand of dye and dyeing temperature. Here generally caustic soda, soda ash or NaHCO₃ is used as alkali depending upon reactivity of dye. They create proper pH in dye bath and do as the dye-fixing agent. The reaction takes place in this stage is shown below:

3 Wash-off:

As the dyeing is completed, a good wash must be applied to the material to remove extra and unfixed dyes from material surface. This is necessary for level dyeing and good wash-fastness. It is done by a series of hot wash, cold wash and soap solution wash.

1.11 Application method of reactive dyes:

Application method of reactive dyes varies significantly with type of dyes, shade required, and available equipments in the mill. These are 3 application procedures available:

1. Discontinuous method-

- Conventional method
- Exhaust or constant temperature method
- High temperature method
- Hot critical method.

2. Continuous method-

- Pad-steam method
- Pad dry method
- Pad thermofix method

3. Semi continuous method-

- Pad roll method
- Pad jig method
- and batch method.

1.12 Stripping of reactive dye:

The reactive dye cannot be satisfactorily stripped from fibre due to covalent bond between dye molecule and fibre. Stripping becomes necessary when uneven dyeing occurs. By stripping azo group ($-N=N-$) from the dye is removed[11]. Now the stripping processes are described:-

Partial stripping:

Partial stripping is obtained by treating the dyed fabric with dilute acetic acid or formic acid. Here temperature is raised to 70-100°C and treatment is continued until shade is removed by desired amount. After that a thorough washing is necessary to remove the product of hydrolysis. The amount of acid used is as below: –

- Glacial acetic acid : 5-10 parts
- With water : 1000 parts

Or

- Formic acid : 2.5 to 10 parts
- With water : 1000 parts
- Temperature : 70 – 100°C
- Time : until desired shade is obtained.

Full stripping:

For complete stripping the goods are first treated with sodium hydrosulphite (hydrosul) at boil then washed off and bleached with 1% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) at room temperature. This is carried out for 30 min.

The recipe is as below:

- Na-hypochlorite : 1% at room temperature
- Na-hydrosulphite: at boil.
- Time : 30 min

1.13 Hydrolysis of reactive dye:

Under alkaline condition reactive dyes react with the terminal hydroxyl group of cellulose. But if the solution of the dye is kept for long time its concentration drops. Then the dye react with the hydroxyl group of water. This reaction of dye with water is known as hydrolysis of reactive dye. After hydrolysis dye cannot react with fibre. So hydrolysis increases the loss of dyes.

This hydrolysis occurs in two stages. At first the concentration of dye initially increases and then begins to decrease. Whereas the concentration of hydroxyl compound increases continuously. Then the hydroxyl compound cannot react with dye.

1. Hydrolysis of halogen containing reactive dye,

2. Hydrolysis of activated vinyl compound containing dye,

For preventing hydrolysis the following precautions are taken—

- As hydrolysis increases with increasing temperature during dissolving and application temperature should not be more than 40°C.
- Dye and alkali solution are prepared separately and mixed just before using.
- Dye and alkali should not be kept for long time after mixing.

1.14 Important factors for dyeing cellulosic fibre with cold brand reactive dye in batching process:

pH of the dye bath: The optimum pH for fixing cold brand reactive dyes on cotton and viscose rayon depends on individual dyes, the temperature and time of dyeing[12]. pH decreases with increasing temperature and time of dyeing. For most of the dyes the optimum pH is 10.8 to 11 at 20o to 25oC. Soda ash has been the best alkali for dyeing at 30oC for cotton, mercerized cotton and linen. Increased fixation (due to higher temperature) and increased dye bath stability and better reproducibility are the advantages of soda ash as the fixing agent.

Amount of Alkali: The amount of alkali used for fixing depends on the depth of shade dyed and the liquor ratio employed. Some quantities of alkali required for fixing the reactive dyes are given table 28.

Dyeing temperature: Since increase in temperature affects the rate of physical and chemical processes involved in dyeing, it is important in dyeing reactive dyes also. The affinity of the dye for the fibre decreases with increases in temperature and at the same time the rate of hydrolysis of the dye increases and adversely affects the fixation of color yield. However the rate of diffusion of the dye in the fibre increases with increased temperature. At temperatures lower than 20oc, the rate of fixation is very low. Hence for most of the dyes a temperature of 20o to 25oC is the recommended temperature while for some other dyeing at 50o to 60oC with sodium bicarbonate as the alkali gives maximum color value.

Electrolyte concentration: Since reactive dyes have low affinity for cellulose exhausting the dye bath by adding common salt or Glauber's salt prior to fixation can increase the fixation. The amount of salt required producing adequate exhaustion decreases with decreasing liquor ratio. Thus for pale shade on cotton and viscose rayon 15 and 10 g/l of common salt used. The quantities may be increased to 30 and 20 to 30 g/l for medium and deep shades on these fibres[13].

Time of dyeing: Generally the dye may be added in two portions. The salt may also be added in two lots. The exhaustion takes place in 20 to 30 min. There is generally no advantage in extending the period beyond 30 min. The alkali is then added and the dyeing continued for 30 to 90 min. The depth of shade and reactivity of the dye decide the time of dyeing. For deeper shades larger times are required.

Liquor ratio: With decreased liquor ratio, both exhaustion and fixation take place to increase exert. However the rate of fixation of most of the dyes is not significantly affected. As the liquor ratio is decreased, the effectiveness of increasing salt addition also decreases. Hence lower amount of salt are sufficient to get optimum exhaustion.

1.1 Low affinity reactive dyes are preferred for dyeing

If the reactivity of the dye is increased considerably, the rate of reaction with the fibre increases[14]. Therefore, the dyeing can be carried out in a short time. However in this case the rate of dye also increases, leading to deactivation of a part of the dye. This results in wastage of the dye. If on the other hand the reactivity of the dye is decreased, the extent of hydrolysis can be reduced considerably.

However, this results in the slower rate of reaction with the fibre also. The ultimate object of dyeing is to react as much of the dye as possible with the fibre and minimize the hydrolysis of the dye. This is achieved in practice in two stages. The dyeing is first started from the aqueous medium under neutral conditions when the dye does not react either with the fibre or with water. Then gluber salt or common salt is added to exhaust the dye onto the fibre as much as possible. In this respect, this stage of dyeing (exhaustion) resembles the dyeing of direct dyes on cotton. Then the second step (that of fixation or reaction with the fibre) is carried out by adding the alkali (usually used soda ash). Since the exhausted dye is already on the fibre, it is more likely that the exhausted dye reacts with the fibre in preference to water.

However the dye present in the dye bath (which contains a substantial amount of the reactive dye) can now react with water since it is under alkaline condition. It is already stated that the hydrolyzed dye cannot further react with the fibre but dye to the affinity forces; it is absorbed by the fibre and is retained in it. During the subsequent washing or soaping the substantivity held hydrolyzed dye gets stripped into the washing bath thereby reducing the washing fastness of the dyeing. If the affinity of the original dye is reduced to a very low value, this problem will not arise and a rigorous treatment of the dyeing with boiling soap or detergent solution removes almost all hydrolyzed dye. However if the affinity is very low, exhaustion of the dye bath prior to fixation cannot be achieved substantially. This results in a larger amount of the reactive dye remaining in the dye bath and getting hydrolyzed when alkali is added subsequently.

If the dye has high affinity for cellulose like a direct dye, it becomes difficult to remove the hydrolyzed dye from the dyeing since it is also absorbed by and retained in the fibre by fairly strong affinity forces, though not as strong as the covalent bond formed between the dye and the fibre. Hence in actual practice low affinity dyes are selected for converting in to reactive dyes.

1.2 Different methods of reactive dye application:

1. Pad-batch method.
 - a. Pad (alkali)-batch (cold) process.
 - b. Pad (alkali)-batch (warm or hot) process.
2. Pad dry method
3. Pad steam method.

1. Pad-batch method:

a. Pad (alkali)-batch (cold) process:

Fig. 2: Pad-batch cold) method

Steps:

1. The fabric is first padded in a padding mangle with reactive dye in presence of an alkali.
2. The padded fabric is rolled in a batch and the batches are wrapped by polyethylene sheets and stored in wet condition for 1-24 hours at 200-300C in a room.
3. During the storage period, the rolls may be kept slowly rotating to prevent seepage of the dye liquor.
4. After storing time is finished fabric is washed in a rope washing machine to remove the unfixed dye from fabric surface.

b. Pad batch (hot) process:

Fig. 3: Pad batch (hot) process

Steps:

1. The fabric is first padded in a padding mangle with reactive dye in presence of an alkali.
2. The fabric is then passed in between infrared heater to preheat the padded fabric to 500C to 900C.
3. The fabric is then batched on a large diameter roller in a hot chamber. The batching is done under controlled conditions of temperature and humidity for a sufficient time to ensure diffusion and fixation of the dye in the fibre. During this period the batch is kept slowly rotating to avoid the seepage of dye liquor.
4. The cloth is then washed in a rope washing machine to remove the unfixed dyes.

2) Pad dry method:

Fig. 4: Pad dry method

Steps:

1. Fabric is first padded in a padder with reactive dye in presence of an alkali.
2. Padded fabric is then passed through a squeezing roller into a dryer. As a dryer cylinder, stenter may be used. During drying due to higher temperature fixation of dye in fibre increases and at the same time water is removed by evaporation.
3. After drying fabric is washed in a washing machine to remove unfixed dye.

3) Pad steam method:

Fig. 5: Pad steam method

Steps:

1. Fabric is first padded in a paddler with the dye.
2. It is then passed through between two squeezing roller in a dryer. Drying should be done slowly; otherwise precipitation of dye due to quick removal of water may take place leading to lower color value.
3. After coming out from dryer fabric is padded in a paddler containing salt and alkali. Due to salt exhaustion of dye takes place and due to alkali fixation occurs.
4. Fabric then passed through a steamer where it is kept for 15-19 second. Due to high temperature here fixation rate increases.
5. In this step fabric is washed in a washing machine to remove the unfixed dye.

1.17 Function of these ingredients:

1. Anti-creasing agent is used to remove crease mark from fabric.
2. Sequestering agent is used to convert hard water into soft water.
3. Gluber salt is used for exhaustion of dye in the fibre.
4. Soda ash and caustic soda are used for fixation of dye in the fibre.
5. Acetic acid is used for neutralizing the dyed fabric.
6. Soap is used for washing the dyed fibre.

1.18 Procedure:

At first fabric, required water and required anti creasing agent is added in the dye bath. Then sequestering agent and gluber salt of required amount is added in the dye bath. Then the bath is kept rest for 5 minutes. After that reactive dye of required amount is added in the dye bath. After adding dye in the dye bath, the bath is kept for 30 minutes. During this period exhaustion of dye occurs in the fabric. Then required amount of alkali is added for fixation of dye into the fabric. After adding alkali we will wait for 50 minutes and then we will check the shade. If shade is all right then fabric will be taken for after treatment.

1. At first dyed fabric will be treated with hot water at 80 °C for 10 minutes.
2. Then the fabric will be treated with stock solution of acetic acid for 10 minutes at 60 °C for neutralizing the fabric.
3. Then the fabric is washing with soap solution for 15 minutes at 950C.

1.19 K/S value:

K/S (Absorption coefficient (K) and Scattering coefficient (S)) is a value used to determine the depth of color of a dyed fabric. K/S values are used in textile applications to control the color process parameters in dyeing, and finishing of fabrics[15].

K/S value is an important parameter of modern colorimetry, which can indicate the depth of the color of dyed fabric surface. Measurement of K/S value is easily and simple operation in the applied engineering.

Take Reactive Blue B-2GLN as examples in this paper, the relationship between K/S value and the fixing rate with the reactive dyes on cotton fabric was studied. The feasibility of K/S value instead of the traditional washing method for the

determination of reactive dyes fixation rate was also studied. The results show that: the K/S value of the fabric has good linear relationship to the reactive dyes fixation rate by the washing method and the reactive dyes fixation rate can be get from the K/S correction value.

The present study covers the evaluation of color strength and color values of cotton fabrics dyed with Coralite blue FL-R reactive dye and treated with silver nanoparticles using spectrophotometer. The characterized silver nano particles are applied along with flurotriazine based reactive dyes (Coralite Blue FL-R) by exhaust dyeing method on cotton fabrics. The concentrations of silver nanoparticles were standardized for different ppm levels as per the silver nano material supplier's standards. The dye bath was set with sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) (20 gpl concentration) and sodium chloride (NaCl) (20gpl). Temperature and rate of dyeing was monitored at 80°C. The dyed fabric was soaped and washed after dyeing. Evaluation of the reactive dyed fabrics and their characterization studies showed the presence of silver nano-particles embedded on the substrate strongly. However, Silver nano-particles (AGNPs) when coupled with reactive dyes enhanced the overall fastness property of the fabrics. The color strength (K/S) values of AGNP treated fabrics were compared with untreated sample showing change in the reflective values and K/S values[16]. In conclusion the color analysis of cotton fabrics dyed with coralite blue FL-R and treated with silver nanoparticles show difference in their color values when silver nano particle concentrations are varied.

Research Methodology

3. Materials and methods

- Fabric type : S/J Knit Fabric
- Composition : 100% Cotton
- GSM : 155-160
- Padder pressure : 1.5 -2 aPM
- Pick up percentage : 70%

3.1 Machine name:

- Cold pad batch machine
- Open bath dyeing machine
- Small dryer machine.

3.2 Dyes, Chemicals & Auxiliaries:

1. Reactive Dye- Remazol Navy
2. Caustic
3. Soda ash
4. Detergent – Eriopon
5. Leveling Agent

3.3 Experimental Equipment:

1. Beaker
2. Pipette
3. Electric Balance
4. Spoon

5. PH Meter

6. Glass rod

3.4 Machine:

Cold pad batch machine:

The laboratory padder is used for dyeing and finishing application of woven fabrics. The pressure is adjustable and the padder speed is approximately 3 m/min. Depending on the pressure setting and the fabric specification, pick up values between 65 % and 85 % can be reached. The 400 m wide padding mangle with 125 mm diameter is made of NBR rubber and the machine is a solid and compact table design made of stainless steel.

Specifications:

Laboratory padder for resin finishing application of woven fabrics. Padder speed: 5 rpm = 3 m/min. Pressure adjustable (0.1 – 0.6 kg/cm² = 1 – 6 bar) for different applications resulting in different pickups of finishing agents. Depending on pressure setting (normally 0.1 – 0.3 kg/cm² = 1 – 3 bar) and fabric specification (weight and structure), pick up is between 65 % and 85 %. Width: 400 mm, diameter: 125 mm (LP) respectively 200 mm (LDP) Padding mangle made of NBR rubber or Hypalon. Solid and compact table design. All stainless steel design. Plug and play (only electrical and air connection needed). Excellent price value ratio.

Padding mangles specification:

- Length: 400 mm
- Diameter: 125 mm
- Hardness: approx. 70 ° Shore
- Specification:
- Dimensions (W x D x H): 720 x 550 x 755 mm
- Machine weight: 100 kg
- Power consumption: 250 W
- Voltage: Single phase 220 V, 50 Hz
- Max. ambient temperature: 60 °C

Fig. 6: Mathis lab dyeing machine

3.5 Woven Dryer:

Application: Used in textile finishing or drying. All types of fabric can dry on it.

Specifications:

Temp range 40°C to 200°C, preset at 163°C

Supplied with 2 off aluminum
turntables Stainless steel interior

Independent overheat thermostat

High accuracy

Excellent stability

Low chamber uniformity

Options

Capable to hold 3 racks total.

Design:

The exterior is constructed from sheet steel finished in an easy clean powder coated paint. The interior chamber is made from 304 stainless steel. The unit is well insulated and has a double glazed window to view the test chamber. Two rotating turntables of 13.5in diameter are supplied to perform both tests Heated by Incoloy sheathed elements positioned in the base of the unit. The control system comprises of a highly accurate PID temperature controller and an independent overheat thermostat with calibrated scale and tamper proof lock. Temperature is controlled and pre-set at 163°C.

Fig. 7: Fabric Dryer Machine

Procedure:

- ❖ At first all chemical mixed properly. After then fabric dissolve on it at room temperature for 10 min.
- ❖ Set the padder pressure 1.5-2 bar.
- ❖ Sample fabric passed through padder at proper tension for two times.
- ❖ After then washed the Fabric and dried by dryer machine.
- ❖ Finally takes the K/S value

Important of washing:

- To remove starch that applied during fabric manufacturing.
- To soften the garment hand feel and improve bulkiness
- To remove dirt, spots, oil stains that accumulate to the garment at the garment manufacturing processes.
- To remove chemicals used during the printing process and embroidery process
- As mentioned above, sometimes you wash garments to meet customer requirement.
- Washed clothes can be worn directly after purchasing
- To give a faded look or any other colour-tinted look to the garment.
- To stabilise garment shrinkage and dimensional instability
- To improve bulkiness and soft hand feel
- To have an idea about washes, common garment washing types are explained below.

Fig. 8: Dyeing Curve

3.6 Spray-Dyeing Method:

Fig. 9: Spray-Dyeing

3.7 Color strength (K/S)

Reflectance (%) of the dyed fabric samples were measured by using Data color 65 observer spectrophotometer[17]. Strength of any colorant (dyestuff / pigment) is related to absorption property. Kubelka–Munk theory gives us the following relation between reflectance and absorbance, which is given bellow in Equation 1.

$$K/S = \left[\frac{(1-R)^2}{2R} \right] \text{----- (1)}$$

Where R is the reflectance, K is absorbance and S is the scattering. By using the above equation color strength of different samples were measured.

Variable shade %: Single factor experiment design analysis based on variable shade % which is given below in Table 1.

Variable shade %	Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
1	60	30
1.5		
2		
2.5		

In this above experimental single factor analysis we assume the temperature at 60 °C and time for 30 minute and just variable shade% from 1% to 2.5%. After finishing the process we found the suitable shade is 2% became highest the K/S value.

Variable Temp (°C): Single factor experiment design analysis based on variable Temp which is given below in Table 2.

Suitable shade %	Drying Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
2	70	30
	80	
	90	
	100	

From the table 1 we got suitable shade is 2%, assume time for 30 minute and variable temperature from 70 °C to 100 °C. After finishing the process we found the suitable Drying Temp at 90 °C became highest the K/S value.

Changeable Time (Min): Single factor experiment design analysis based on Changeable Time which is given below in Table 3.

Suitable shade %	Drying Temp (°C)	Drying Time (Min)
2	90	5
		10
		15
		20

From the table 2 we got also suitable temperature at 90 °C and time from 5 minute to 20 minute. After finishing the process we found the suitable Drying time for 10 minutes became highest the K/S value.

Variable pick up%: Single factor experiment design analysis based on Changeable picks up% which is given below in

Table 4.

Suitable shade %	Drying Temperature(°)	Drying Time	Variable pick up%
2	90	10	60
			65
			70
			75

From the table 3 we got also suitable drying time for 10 minutes and changeable pick up% from 60 to 75%. After finishing the process we found the suitable pick up 70% became highest the K/S value.

Optimum data analysis: We got the Optimum results from single factor (based on K/S value) above the data analysis which is given below in Table 5.

Suitable shade %	Suitable drying Temp (°C)	Suitable drying Time (Min)	Pick up%
2	90	10	70%

Result Discussion

4. L9 Taguchi Experimental Design analysis

Recent industrial applications have been particularly associated with the name of the Japanese engineer, G. Taguchi. The Taguchi method optimizes design parameters to minimize variation before optimizing design to hit mean target values for output parameters. The Taguchi method uses special orthogonal arrays to study all the design factors with minimum of experiments. The Taguchi method is one of the best experimental methodologies used to find the minimum number of experiments to be performed within the permissible limit of factors and levels[18]. The comparative study was performed for volumetric wear of Nano hydroxyapatite and MTA-filled dental composites using a combination of four factors, each having five levels. The S/N ratio for the smaller is better characteristic was to find the best condition for the minimum volumetric wear rate.

L9 Taguchi Experimental Design analysis design which is given below in Table 6: L9 Design

Run	X1	X2	X3
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	1	3	3
4	2	2	1
5	2	3	2
6	2	1	3
7	3	3	1
8	3	1	2
9	3	2	3

L9 Taguchi Experimental Design analysis which is given below in Table 7.

S/L	Shade%	Drying Temp.	Drying Time	Pick Up%	Fixation Rate%	SNRA1	MEAN1
1.	1.0	80	5	65%	71.30%	37.0618	71.30
2.	1.0	90	10	70%	81.69%	38.2434	81.69
3.	1.0	100	15	75%	82.40%	38.3185	82.40
4.	1.5	80	10	75%	82.19%	38.2964	82.19
5.	1.5	90	15	65%	86.60%	38.7504	86.60
6.	1.5	100	5	70%	82.52%	38.3312	82.52
7.	2.0	80	15	70%	91.56%	39.2341	91.56
8.	2.0	90	5	75%	79.52%	38.0095	79.52
9.	2.0	100	10	65%	88.63%	38.9516	88.63

L9 Taguchi Experimental Design analysis which is given below in Table 8.

S/L	Shade%	Drying Temp.	Drying Time	Pick Up%	Fixation Rate%	SNRA1	MEAN1
1.	1.0	80	5	65%	71.30%	37.0618	71.30
2.	1.0	90	10	70%	81.69%	38.2434	81.69
3.	1.0	100	15	75%	82.40%	38.3185	82.40
4.	1.5	80	10	75%	82.19%	38.2964	82.19
5.	1.5	90	15	65%	86.60%	38.7504	86.60
6.	1.5	100	5	70%	82.52%	38.3312	82.52
7.	2.0	80	15	70%	91.56%	39.2341	91.56
8.	2.0	90	5	75%	79.52%	38.0095	79.52
9.	2.0	100	10	65%	88.63%	38.9516	88.63

4.1 Taguchi Analysis:

Fixation Rate % versus Shade%, Drying Temperature, Drying Time, Pick up%

Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratios

Larger is better

	Level	Shade%	Drying Temperature	Drying Time	Pick up%
	1	37.87	38.20	37.80	38.25
	2	38.46	38.33	38.50	38.60
	3	38.73	38.53	38.77	38.21
Delta		0.86	0.34	0.97	0.39
Rank		2	4	1	3

Response Table for Means

	Level	Shade%	Drying Temperature	Drying Time	Pick up%
	1	78.46	81.68	77.78	82.18
	2	83.77	82.60	84.17	85.26
	3	86.57	84.52	86.85	81.37
Delta		8.11	2.83	9.07	3.89
Rank		2	4	1	3

Graph 1: Response for Signal to Noise Ratios

Graph 2: Response for Means

Conclusions

The dyeing of cotton fabric using a spray dyeing machine, as well as dye fixation treatment, was studied. The combination of wet fixation and drying process and excellent color uniformity properties compared to samples with Reactive drying. The optimal process conditions of spray dyeing were determined using an orthogonal array. We got the suitable result from the above graph first portion shows that suitable shade is 2%, Suitable drying Temp at 90 (0C), Suitable drying Time for 10 (Min) and also Pick up 70%. A new system in the presence of other kinds of dyes such as reactive dye, direct dye, acid dye, base dye, and so on to improve dye fixation rate onto cotton fabric using this spray dyeing technology. Moreover, the developed dyeing process may reduce chemicals and water consumption in textile industries.

References

- [1] Basra, S.A., et al., Analysis of the factors affecting the dimensional stability of socks using full-factorial experimental design method. *Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*, 2020. 15: p. 1558925020948219.
- [2] Stalder, E., *Fashion 101: A crash course in clothing*. 2019: Zest Books™.
- [3] Duhovic, M. and D. Bhattacharyya, Simulating the deformation mechanisms of knitted fabric composites. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2006. 37(11): p. 1897-1915.
- [4] Ravandi, S.H. and M. Valizadeh, Properties of fibers and fabrics that contribute to human comfort, in *Improving comfort in clothing*. 2011, Elsevier. p. 61-78.
- [5] Zhao, S., et al., Development of auxetic warp knitted fabrics based on reentrant geometry. *Textile Research Journal*, 2020. 90(3-4): p. 344-356.
- [6] Lewis, D.M., Developments in the chemistry of reactive dyes and their application processes. *Coloration Technology*, 2014. 130(6): p. 382-412.
- [7] Simoncic, B. and B. Tomsic, Structures of novel antimicrobial agents for textiles-a review. *Textile Research Journal*, 2010. 80(16): p. 1721-1737.
- [8] Khatri, A., et al., A review on developments in dyeing cotton fabrics with reactive dyes for reducing effluent pollution. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2015. 87: p. 50-57.
- [9] Sohel, M., et al., Study on effect on concentration of Soda on dyeing of woven cotton fabric with Reactive dye. 2012, Daffodil International University.

- [10] Meller, A., The chemistry of alkaline degradation of cellulose and oxidized celluloses II. 1960.
- [11]. Aspland, J., Disperse dyes and their application to polyester. *Textile Chemist and Colorist*, 1992. 24: p. 18-18.
- [12] Fowler, J. and C. Preston, The application of Reactive dyes to Viscose Rayon. *Journal of the Society of Dyers and Colourists*, 1958. 74(5): p. 372-381.
- [13]. Maulik, S.R., et al., Vat Dye and Its Evolution in Dyeing. *Textile Dyes and Pigments: A Green Chemistry Approach*, 2022: p. 87-105.
- [14]. Vickerstaff, T., Reactive dyes for textiles. *Journal of the Society of Dyers and Colourists*, 1957. 73(6): p. 237-245.
- [15]. Ramaiah, G.B. and A.P. Ari. Evaluation of color strength (K/S) values of cotton fabrics dyed with reactive dye and treated with silver nanoparticles. in *AIP Conference Proceedings*. 2019. AIP Publishing LLC.
- [16] Butola, B. and A. Kumar, Green chemistry based in-situ synthesis of silver nanoparticles for multifunctional finishing of chitosan polysaccharide modified cellulosic textile substrate. *International journal of biological macromolecules*, 2020. 152: p. 1135-1145.
- [17]. Zhang, G., et al., Spectrophotometric color matching for pre-colored fiber blends based on a hybrid of least squares and grid search method. *Textile Research Journal*, 2022. 92(15-16): p. 2569-2579.
- [18]. Kurt, M., E. Bagci, and Y. Kaynak, Application of Taguchi methods in the optimization of cutting parameters for surface finish and hole diameter accuracy in dry drilling processes. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 2009. 40: p. 458-469.

List of Authors

Dipta Barua
b.diptaaa@gmail.com

Md. Iusuf Khan

IusufKhan50@gmail.com

Asst. Professor, Dept. of Textile Engineering,
Port City International University

Address: 7-14 Nikunja Housing Society, South Khulshi, Chattogram, Bangladesh

Sattyajit Sikder

Skshuba34@gmail.com

Avijit Dev BTE 01706134
Avijitdev13@gmail.com

Rabaca Sultana
rabaca954@gmail.com

Taryqul Islam Aulve
aulve.swi@gmail.com

Mehedi Hasan Ibhanraj
ibhanraj45@gmail.com

Tonmoy Palit
tonmoypalit315@gmail.com

